

8T – Spin and Stability

"The Truth is always simpler than you think." Richard Feynman.

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Abstract:

The paper presents a prediction regarding spin stability using the primordial coupling series. The stability of a Boson is directly proportional to spin and inversely proportional to the number of distinct or equivalent prime net variations which appear outside of the parenthesis. The more elements appear, the shorter the lifetime of the Boson and the faster it should decay. Similar predictions are made in other theories such as QFT regarding high spin particles. The methods and reasoning is different, as those theories did not use the Primordial function of coupling constants, derived in March 2021.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

We classified Gravity a varying interaction that is a composite of three distinct or equivalent net curvatures, which was by equations (2.2-2.3) in the 8T thesis:

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} = \left[2N_{gravity} + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (2.2)$$

$$[2N_{gravity} + 2] \rightarrow [2N_{gravity}] \quad (2.3)$$

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK3}$$

$$[N_{VK1}, N_{VK2}, N_{VK3}] \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$K1 \dots KN \in \mathbb{R}$$

Another possible composition, among infinity of others:

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK4}$$

$$N_{VK3} \neq N_{VK4}$$

The structure of the gravity is invariant to the change of the element. Since the total spin is invariant, i.e. two, there is not a change in the nature of gravity; the structure is the same while the composite element could be different. The spin two indicate short range, which agrees with the idea of inner curvature, and with the lack of detecting the graviton. The spin two vanish to an even number in net curvature representation. As equation (2.3) indicate, that is how we derived the Graviton is massless.

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK3} \rightarrow 2N_0 + 2$$

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK4} \rightarrow 2N_0 + 2$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals that were needed for the rest of the paper. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. The spin classification allows us a glimpse onto another feature of the primordial not before mentioned, spin stability. The higher the spin, the more elements are participating in the composition of the Bosons. There is always a chances one or more than more of those composite elements will somehow depart and could join to a distinct coupling term, thus the spin will vary and the Boson will decay to a lower spin state. That is **only true** to interactions that are **composite**, i.e. spin higher than one. These are not independent and subject to time variance. That is preciously the reason we introduced the invariant structure of gravity to variation of its elements. Three predictions can be made under the scope of the primordial:

- (1) There exist no limitation to the spin a Boson can get, there exist spin three particle.
- (2) There exist a relation between spin and stability.
 - (2.1) the stability of a Boson is inversely proportional to the number of net variation elements present in the coupling term. The most stable, therefore are the independent interactions conation one element of net variation.
 - (2.2) The lifetime and the range of a given Boson is inversely proportional to the number of net variation elements present in the coupling term.

That is somewhat resembles the formation of linear algebra, trying to classify the independent base of a certain date set, which using that set we can create those higher terms which are composite. In the 8T submitted proof of the Riemann hypothesis, it was proved that those higher primes could be created by using odd number of lower primes (The proof was based on the anti-commutation relation of Fermions). That is similar to the invariant structure of gravity. Nature does not tell us which prime to use, and thus we derived the variance of those composite interactions. The emphasis of this paper is that this variance trait implies instability, short range and short lifetime.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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